

Hemp Club

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Competent and Connected
Clusters Unfold the Hemp
Industry Potential for the
European Bioeconomy

What we do

The HempClub project brings together **7 clusters and associations** operating in the bioeconomy, advanced manufacturing and hemp production sectors to create **interconnected and interregional supply chains** between operators in primary production, agri-food processing and green chemistry by strengthening industrial symbiosis and sustainable and renewable business models in the **hemp sector**.

- ❖ Improve the **management skills** of cluster managers.
- ❖ Strengthen **cluster excellence capacity** by improving the portfolio of business support services.
- ❖ **Facilitate B2B and C2C collaborative activities** to strengthen interregional strategies for the bioeconomy
- ❖ Enhance **collaboration** and **networking** activities between European organisations.
- ❖ Promote **internationalisation, technology** and **knowledge transfer** through the activation of new opportunities for growth and capacity of excellence for clusters and their members.

Why hemp?

With its **unique chemical properties, environmental benefits, high yield** and **wide range of applications**, hemp is a valuable crop for the bioeconomy, contributing to achieving climate neutrality, although still representing a niche crop in Europe.

ClusterXChange

- ❖ ClusterXchange is a new pilot scheme to support **short-term exchanges** to better connect Europe's industrial ecosystems. It facilitates transnational cooperation, peer learning, networking and innovation uptake between actors of different industrial clusters.
- ❖ The project will carry out at least **80 short-term exchanges** involving SMEs, scale supports organizations, training providers, public authorities and big companies involved or interested in the **hemp sector** and belonging to a COSME participating country.
- ❖ Exchanges will include several activities such as **on-the-job-training** for visiting participants, **sharing of information and experience** between visiting organisation and host organisation, **enhancing market access** and **identification of potential partners** for new cluster organisations and other scaling-up support organisations, **supporting the networking** between clusters.
- ❖ Most of these exchanges will have a duration of **five working days** with a distance between the two involved organisations more than 200 kilometres. A **lump sum** will be provided to support accommodation and living costs during the exchange.

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